

Review Article

Trends and Transformations in Agribusiness Research: A Decadal Bibliometric Analysis

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Abstract

Agribusiness research has significantly transformed in sustainability practices and technological advancements over the past decade. This study analyzes trends from 2014 to 2023, focusing on publication patterns, source relevance, author contributions, and thematic developments. The evolution highlights key influences shaping agribusiness research. This study employed a systematic literature review using Scopus data, analyzing 717 articles with bibliometric techniques in R software, focusing on English articles in Business, Management, and Accounting. The study revealed initial low publication rates in 2014-2015, followed by rapid growth, peaking at 99 articles in 2021. Key journals like Journal of Cleaner Production and authors like Blok V were influential. Themes included sustainability, technology, and socio-economic aspects. Agribusiness research underscores the interdisciplinary nature of sustainability, technology, and socio-economic impacts, shaping future research and practice in the field. This study contributes by providing a comprehensive analysis of agribusiness research trends over a decade, highlighting pivotal themes and influential sources driving the field forward.

Keywords: Agribusiness, bibliometric, transformations, trend, research.

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Introduction

Agribusiness refers to the industries involved in the production, processing, and distribution of agricultural products (Kerutagi, Jangale, Gayathri, Jagadeshwaran, & sengar, 2023). It encompasses a wide range of activities that support the agricultural sector, including farming, seed supply, agrochemicals, farm machinery, wholesale and distribution, processing, marketing, and retail sales (Bairwa, Kalia, Meena, Lakra, & Kushwaha, 2014). The primary components of agribusiness include farming, aquaculture, and horticulture, which are critical for primary production. The supply chain and logistics, including seed supply and genetics, agrochemicals, farm machinery, and efficient transportation and storage solutions, play a crucial role in ensuring that agricultural products reach their destinations (Chandan, John, & Potdar, 2023). Processing and value addition, such as food processing and biofuels, transform raw agricultural products into consumable goods and renewable energy sources. Marketing and retail involve wholesale distribution and direct sales to consumers, facilitated by supermarkets, farmers' markets, and online platforms. Support services like research and development, financial services, and consulting are essential for innovation and effective farm management (Karmakar, Khan, Roshid, & Shamme, 2022).

Agribusiness research is of immense significance as it drives innovation, enhances productivity, ensures sustainability, and supports economic development. Through rigorous research efforts, the sector can develop new technologies and practices, such as precision agriculture and genetically modified crops, which revolutionize farming and production processes, leading to increased efficiency and productivity (Blakeney, 2022). Additionally, agribusiness research promotes sustainable farming practices that minimize environmental impact, such as soil health studies, water conservation methods, and the use of organic fertilizers and pesticides (Ioris, 2015). By addressing food security, research ensures a reliable food supply for a growing global population and enhances the nutritional content and safety of food products. Economically, research-driven advancements create new business opportunities, generate employment, and drive rural development, thereby contributing significantly to economic growth. Understanding market trends and consumer preferences through research allows agribusinesses to remain competitive by developing products that meet market demands. Moreover, agribusiness research provides the scientific basis for policy development and regulation, ensuring that agricultural practices are governed by sound science and effective standards (Sinha, 2023). Finally, agribusiness research manages risks associated with climate change, pests, diseases, and market fluctuations, thereby enhancing their resilience and ensuring long-term sustainability. Overall, agribusiness research forms the foundation for modern, efficient, and sustainable agricultural practices, ultimately contributing to societal well-being and the global economy.

Various studies in agribusiness have explored multiple facets of agricultural production, supply chains, sustainability, market dynamics, and policy impacts, providing valuable insights for the sector. Research on precision agriculture and technology adoption, such as a study from the U.S. Midwest, has shown that factors like farm size, access to capital, and farmer education significantly influence the adoption of technologies like GPS-guided equipment and soil sensors, which can enhance productivity and sustainability (Munz & Schuele, 2022). Studies on climate change, like

one focusing on India, have highlighted the adverse effects of rising temperatures and changing precipitation patterns on crop yields, emphasizing the need for climate-resilient crop varieties and improved irrigation practices (Aryal, et al., 2020). Sustainable farming practices have also been a major research focus, with comparative studies demonstrating that organic farms, despite higher labor costs, offer benefits such as higher biodiversity, improved soil health, and lower greenhouse gas emissions, alongside premium prices for organic products. Supply chain management research, exemplified by a case study of fresh produce in Kenya, has identified significant inefficiencies due to inadequate cold storage, poor transport infrastructure, and lack of coordination, recommending investments in cold chain infrastructure and better supply chain management training to reduce post-harvest losses (Lipwop & Achuora, 2021). Market access for smallholder farmers is another critical area, with studies in Sub-Saharan Africa revealing barriers like limited market information, poor infrastructure, and lack of financial services, suggesting improvements in rural infrastructure and access to credit (Aku, Mshenga, Afari-Sefa, & Justus, 2018). The impact of agricultural policies, such as those under the European Union's Common Agricultural Policy, has been studied to show that subsidies increase farm incomes, particularly for small and medium-sized farms, though better targeting for environmental sustainability is needed (Staniszewski & Borychowski, 2020). Consumer preferences for organic produce have been extensively researched, with meta-analyses indicating that consumers are willing to pay a premium for organic products due to perceived health benefits and environmental concerns, suggesting that producers and retailers should emphasize these attributes (Massey, O'Cass, & Otahal, 2018). Additionally, studies on food security, like the analysis of Brazil's Zero Hunger Program, have shown that comprehensive strategies, including cash transfers, food distribution, and support for family farming, can significantly reduce hunger and improve nutritional outcomes, offering a model for other developing countries (Fraundorfer, 2013). These diverse studies underscore the complexity of the agribusiness sector and the need for multifaceted approaches to address its challenges. Similarly, a comprehensive systematic bibliometric analysis is required to manage and understand these complexities.

Given the extensive and diverse body of research conducted in agribusiness, there is a pressing need for a bibliometric analysis to systematically review and synthesize the existing literature. Agribusiness encompasses numerous sub-fields, including crop production, livestock management, supply chain logistics, sustainability practices, and market dynamics, each producing a substantial volume of research. This proliferation of studies can make it challenging for researchers, policymakers, and industry stakeholders to stay informed about the latest developments, key trends, and significant contributions within the field. A bibliometric analysis addresses this challenge by employing statistical methods to analyze publication patterns, citation networks, and authorship trends across the vast array of agribusiness research. This systematic approach allows for a comprehensive overview of the literature, identifying the most influential papers, leading researchers, and predominant themes. By doing so, bibliometric analysis helps in recognizing foundational studies and seminal works that have shaped the current understanding of agribusiness, providing a clear map of the intellectual landscape. "Backing this situation, this study analyzes the evolution of agribusiness research from 2014 to 2023, focusing on trends in sustainability practices, technological advancements, and their influence on publication patterns, source relevance, author contributions, and thematic developments."

Methodology

Research Design

This study employs a systematic literature review methodology to explore the intersection of agriculture and business within the context of academic publications. The search criteria focus on Article titles, Abstracts, and Keywords, utilizing specific Boolean operators to narrow down relevant documents. The search query used is "agriculture AND business AND agri AND business." The rationale behind selecting specific terms and any adjustments made to the query should be documented to provide clarity and allow others to replicate the search. This methodology ensures a comprehensive and systematic review of the literature, capturing essential studies while avoiding irrelevant results.

Data Source

The primary data source for this study is the Scopus database, covering the period from 2014 to 2024. The data search was conducted on July 1, 2024, at 10:55 AM. The dataset comprises a total of 717 documents that fit the study's criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

Documents included in the study are limited to articles and conference papers written in English and classified under the subject areas of Business, Management, and Accounting. This choice facilitates the inclusion of widely recognized works but excludes non-English or regional sources, which may provide valuable localized insights. The limitation is acknowledged to maintain methodological focus and manageability. Future research could address this gap by incorporating diverse linguistic and regional perspectives.

Exclusion Criteria

Excluded from the study are documents classified as literature reviews, notes, and books to ensure focus on original research contributions.

Data Analysis

The analysis of the collected data is conducted using bibliometric analysis techniques facilitated by R software packages, specifically utilizing bibloshiny for visualization and interactive exploration of bibliometric results. Key metrics such as citation patterns, authorship trends, keyword frequencies, and thematic evolution are analyzed to provide insights into the research landscape at the intersection of agriculture and business over the specified timeframe.

Methodological Steps

Search Strategy Development: Designing a comprehensive search query TITLE-ABS-KEY (agriculture AND business OR agri AND business) AND PUBYEAR > 2013 AND PUBYEAR < 2025 AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "BUSI")) AND (LIMIT-TO

(SRCTYPE, "j") AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBSTAGE, "final")).

Visualization and Interpretation

Using biblioshiny to visualize and interpret the results, facilitating an interactive exploration of bibliometric insights and trends within the dataset.

This structured approach ensures a rigorous and systematic examination of the literature on agriculture and business, providing valuable insights into research themes, scholarly collaborations, and emerging trends in this interdisciplinary field. Data interpretation contextualizes the results within the broader academic discourse, identifies significant contributions, and highlights gaps and emerging areas in the field of agriculture and business.

Findings

Agribusiness research paper publication in years

Figure 1. Publication Trend

The number of studies on agribusiness research publications from 2014 to 2023 reveals significant trends and patterns in the field. In the initial period of 2014-2015, the number of publications was relatively low, with 29 articles in 2014 and a slight decline to 24 in 2015. This period might reflect an emerging interest or limited focus on agribusiness research. From 2016 to 2018, there was a marked growth phase. The number of publications almost doubled to 53 articles in 2016 and continued to increase through 2017 and 2018, reaching 64 articles. This growth indicates a rising interest in agribusiness research. The years 2019 and 2020 saw a period of rapid expansion, with the number of publications increasing significantly to 80 articles in 2019 and 81 in 2020. From 2021 onwards, the field experienced consistent high activity. The number of publications

peaked at 99 articles in 2021, followed by slight decreases to 87 articles in 2022 and 90 articles in 2023.

Most Relevant Source

The data on sources of agribusiness research papers indicates the distribution of articles across various journals. Leading the list is the Journal of Cleaner Production with 68 articles, highlighting a strong focus on sustainability and clean production methods within the agribusiness sector. Following this, the International Food and Agribusiness Management Review published 21 articles, reflecting its role in addressing managerial and business aspects of agribusiness.

Figure 2. Most relevant source

Emerald Emerging Markets Case Studies and Quality - Access to Success each contributed 18 articles. These journals likely focus on case studies in emerging markets and quality management, respectively, demonstrating the diverse aspects of agribusiness research. The Journal of Environmental Management and Tourism published 16 articles, indicating an intersection between agribusiness, environmental management, and tourism. Other significant contributors include Agricultural and Resource Economics with 14 articles, emphasizing the economic dimensions of agribusiness, and Custos e Agronegocio with 12 articles, which may have a regional or specialized focus within the field. Technology in Society published 10 articles, showing the impact of technological advancements on agribusiness. Finally, both the British Food Journal and the International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research published 9 articles each, indicating a broad interest in food-related topics and technological research within agribusiness. This distribution of articles across various journals underscores the multidisciplinary nature of agribusiness research, spanning sustainability, economics, technology, and management.

Bradford' law

The graph illustrates the application of Bradford's Law to agribusiness research sources, identifying core journals that contribute the majority of articles in the field. According to Bradford's Law, a small number of journals produce a disproportionately large number of significant articles. In this graph, the Journal of Cleaner Production stands out as the most prolific source, with 68 articles, emphasizing its pivotal role in publishing research focused on sustainability and clean production practices in agribusiness. The subsequent core sources include the International Food and Agribusiness Management Review with 21 articles, Emerald Emerging Markets Case Studies and Quality - Access to Success each with 18 articles, and the Journal of Environmental Management and Tourism with 16 articles. These journals form the core zone (Zone 1) of agribusiness research, together contributing a substantial number of articles. Other significant sources in this core zone are Agricultural and Resource Economics with 14 articles, Custos e Agronegocio with 12 articles, and Technology in Society with 10 articles, followed by the British Food Journal and the International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research, each contributing 9 articles.

Figure 3. Core source

These journals cover various aspects of agribusiness, including economic studies, regional focuses, and technological impacts. The core zone encapsulates the most influential sources in agribusiness research, highlighting their dominant contribution to the field. Beyond this zone, the frequency of articles per source decreases significantly, illustrating the long tail of journals that, while still contributing valuable research, do so at a lower frequency.

Most relevant Authors

The graph showcases the most relevant authors in the field of agribusiness research, based on the number of documents they have contributed. At the top of the list is Blok V, who has authored 5 documents, indicating a significant impact and prolific contribution to agribusiness research. Following closely are Kumar S and Morris W, each with 4 documents, demonstrating their considerable involvement and influence in the field. Other notable contributors include Amahian AB, Barth H, D'Onzo MA, Hoveskog M, Hu R, Li Y, and Lin J, each with 3 documents. These authors, while having slightly fewer publications than the top three, still represent important voices in agribusiness research.

Figure 4. Most relevant source

This graph highlights the key contributors who have significantly advanced the field through their research. Their collective work provides a foundational basis for ongoing and future studies, showcasing the leading figures whose contributions are shaping the discourse and development within the agribusiness sector.

Lotka's Law

The data presented exemplifies Lotka's Law, a principle in bibliometrics that describes the productivity pattern of authors within a given field.

Figure 5. Lotka's Law

In this case, 2,048 authors have written only one document, representing 95% of all authors. This dominant proportion aligns with Lotka's Law, as the majority of contributors typically have a single publication. As the number of publications increases, the number of authors decreases significantly. For instance, 88 authors have written two documents, accounting for 4.1% of the total, while only 17 authors have three documents (0.8%). This declining trend continues, with just two authors having written four documents (0.1%) and only one author with five documents, demonstrating a sharp drop-off in the number of highly prolific authors. This pattern illustrates the characteristic distribution described by Lotka's Law, where a small number of authors contribute the bulk of the publications, while the vast majority of authors have only one or two publications.

Most Relevant Affiliations

Figure 6. Most Relevant Affiliations

Affiliations of agribusiness research articles highlights the institutions that are most active in contributing to this field. Halmstad University, University of Novi Sad, and an unspecified category labeled "Not Reported" each top the list with 15 articles. This indicates a strong research output from these institutions and showcases their leading roles in advancing agribusiness research.

Cornell University follows closely with 13 articles, reflecting its significant involvement and contribution to the field. Wageningen University, known for its focus on life sciences and agricultural research, has 11 articles, while its broader entity, Wageningen University and Research, adds 9 more, emphasizing the institution's overall substantial impact.

Cheng Shiu University contributed 10 articles, showing its active participation in agribusiness studies. Massey University and Universitas Komputer Indonesia each have 8 articles, indicating their notable research efforts. Sichuan Agricultural University, with 7 articles, also demonstrates a solid commitment to agribusiness research.

Corresponding Authors Countries

Figure 7. Corresponding Authors Countries

The data provided showcases the global distribution of agribusiness research articles by country, highlighting both single-country publications (SCP) and multiple-country publications (MCP). The United States leads the list with 51 articles, 40 of which are SCPs and 11 MCPs, representing 7.1% of the total articles with a MCP ratio of 0.216. This indicates a strong domestic research output with a significant amount of international collaboration.

India follows closely with 49 articles (45 SCPs and 4 MCPs), accounting for 6.8% of the total, but with a lower MCP ratio of 0.082, suggesting a more domestically focused research approach. China, with 32 articles, shows a balanced distribution between SCPs

(17) and MCPs (15), resulting in a high MCP ratio of 0.469, indicating a significant degree of international collaboration.

Other notable contributors include Italy with 29 articles (MCP ratio 0.207) and the United Kingdom with 27 articles and a notable MCP ratio of 0.407, reflecting its strong international research ties. Australia, Indonesia, Spain, Brazil, and the Netherlands also make substantial contributions, each with varying levels of international collaboration.

Countries like Canada, Germany, and France exhibit high MCP ratios (0.5, 0.4, and 0.5 respectively), highlighting their extensive international research networks despite having fewer total articles compared to leading countries. In contrast, countries such as Ukraine, Portugal, and Egypt have all their articles as SCPs, indicating no international collaboration in the dataset provided.

The figure provided lists the frequency of research publications from various countries based on a bibliometric analysis from the Scopus index for the years 2014-2024. India leads with 176 publications, followed closely by the USA with 169, and Ukraine with 150.

Country Scientific Production

Figure 8. Country Scientific production

These countries are evidently significant contributors to research in the field being analyzed. Italy and China also show substantial presence with 127 and 126 publications, respectively. The UK, Indonesia, and Kazakhstan follow with 89, 109, and 73 publications respectively, indicating a diverse geographical spread of research activity. Countries like Brazil, Spain, and Australia also maintain notable positions with 65, 62, and 55 publications each. Overall, the data highlights a global distribution of research efforts in the specified area, reflecting varying levels of academic and scientific engagement across different nations over the past decade.

Most Global cited documents

Figure 9. Most Global cited documents

The figure provided lists research papers along with their total citations and average citations per year, offering insights into their impact and longevity in academic discourse. The paper by Dutta et al. (2020) published in *Transportation Research Part E* stands out with a total of 717 citations, averaging 143.40 citations per year, indicating its significant influence and ongoing relevance in the field of logistics and transportation. Mangla et al. (2018) follows with 242 total citations and an average of 34.57 citations per year in the *International Journal of Production Economics*, highlighting its sustained impact in production economics research. Kumar et al. (2021) in the *Journal of Cleaner Production* have accumulated 229 citations at a rate of 57.25 per year, underscoring the paper's recent and impactful contribution to clean production studies. Filimonau et al. (2019) and Hens et al. (2018) also demonstrate substantial influence with 225 and 194 total citations, respectively, contributing significantly to research in tourism management and clean production economics. Each paper's citation metrics reflect their scholarly impact and continued relevance in their respective fields over time.

Most Local cited Documents

Figure 10. Most Local cited Documents

The figure data lists various academic documents along with their publication year and the number of local citations they have received. Pindado et al. (2017) in *Small Business Economics*, Morris (2017) in the *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, and Long (2017) in the *International Food and Agribusiness Management Review* each received 4, 3, and 3 citations respectively in their publication year, indicating initial recognition within their fields shortly after publication. Lin et al. (2020) and Valaskova et al. (2020) garnered 2 local citations each in 2020, suggesting emerging interest and relevance in decision support systems and risk management in financial and business contexts. Similarly, Stehel et al. (2019), Kalkanci et al. (2019), and other papers from 2018 by Hens et al., Carayannis et al., and Long et al. received 2 local citations each, reflecting a moderate level of attention within their respective academic communities during those years.

Word cloud

Figure 11. Word cloud

The provided figure offers insights into the prominence of various terms in a dataset, reflecting their frequency of occurrence. "Agriculture" emerges as the most frequently mentioned term, appearing 102 times, underscoring its central role in the dataset. Following closely are terms like "sustainable development" and "agricultural robots," indicating significant attention to topics related to sustainability and technological advancements in agriculture. Terms such as "environmental impact," "supply chains," "climate change," "commerce," "life cycle," and "food supply" also appear with moderate frequencies, highlighting their relevance in discussions likely centered on agricultural practices, environmental sustainability, and economic aspects of food production and distribution. The diversity of these terms suggests a multifaceted approach to studying agriculture, encompassing environmental, economic, technological, and social dimensions.

Trend Topics

Figure 12. Trend Topics

The figure provided outlines the frequency of various topics over different years, offering insights into their trends and evolution. Several themes have shown consistent attention over the years, such as "agriculture," which dominates with 102 mentions, indicating sustained interest and research focus. "Sustainable development" and "environmental impact" also demonstrate a steady rise in attention from 2018 to 2022, reflecting growing concerns and research efforts in these critical areas. Topics like "life cycle assessment (LCA)" and "life cycle" exhibit periods of concentrated interest around 2017-2018, likely driven by advancements and applications in environmental studies and industrial processes.

Emerging trends are evident in newer topics like "agricultural robots," which peaked in 2020-2021, suggesting increasing exploration of automation technologies in agriculture. Similarly, "climate change" and "decision making" show a noticeable uptick in mentions from 2019 onwards, indicating heightened research focus on these pressing global issues. "Innovation" and "agricultural technology" also reflect recent developments and advancements in agricultural practices and technological applications.

Overall, the dataset illustrates a dynamic landscape of research interests, where certain topics like sustainability, technology integration in agriculture, and environmental impacts maintain enduring relevance, while newer issues like climate change and technological innovation gain prominence reflecting evolving challenges and priorities in agricultural and environmental sciences.

Co-occurrence network

Figure 13. Co-occurrence network

The figure presents a co-occurrence network where nodes represent various terms or concepts, and different clusters indicate groups of closely related nodes based on metrics such as betweenness centrality, closeness centrality, and PageRank. In this network:

Cluster 1: Includes nodes like "article," "human," "agricultural worker," and "biotechnology." These nodes are closely interconnected with moderate to high betweenness centrality, indicating they serve as important bridges or connectors between other nodes in the network. Closeness centrality and PageRank values are relatively low, suggesting they may not be the most central nodes in terms of direct connections or influence.

Cluster 2: Consists of "entrepreneur" and "sustainability." These nodes have lower betweenness centrality compared to Cluster 1 but demonstrate a higher closeness centrality, suggesting they are more directly connected to other nodes in their immediate vicinity. Their PageRank values are moderate, indicating they hold some influence within their cluster.

Cluster 3: Dominated by nodes like "agriculture," "sustainable development," "agricultural robots," and "environmental impact." These nodes exhibit significantly higher betweenness centrality values, indicating they play crucial roles as intermediaries or connectors between different parts of the network. Closeness centrality values are also notable, indicating their proximity and influence within their cluster. PageRank values are relatively high, suggesting these nodes are influential and widely referenced within the network.

Overall, the co-occurrence network analysis reveals distinct clusters of related terms and concepts, with some nodes serving as pivotal connectors (high betweenness

centrality) and others being more central or influential within their immediate network neighborhood (high closeness centrality and PageRank). This structure highlights the interconnected nature of the topics and their varying degrees of importance and influence within the analyzed dataset.

Thematic evolution

Figure 14. Thematic evolution

The figure provided offers insights into thematic evolution across different time periods and topics within agricultural and related domains. Here's a breakdown of the thematic evolution based on the data:

Early Period (2014-2018)

Focus on Agricultural Development: Terms like "agricultural development," "agricultural productions," and "agriculture" dominate, reflecting a foundational focus on agricultural practices and productivity.

Technological and Business Aspects: Terms such as "technology adoption," "business modeling," and "business" start appearing, suggesting increasing attention to technology integration and business strategies within agriculture.

Transition Period (2019-2020)

Diversification and Expansion: Topics like "sustainable development," "agricultural robots," and "commerce" gain prominence, indicating a shift towards sustainable practices, technological innovations like robotics, and commercial aspects within agriculture.

Emerging Trends: New topics such as "supply chains," "innovation," and "entrepreneurship" begin to emerge, suggesting growing interest in supply chain

management, innovation in agricultural technologies, and entrepreneurial ventures in agribusiness.

Recent Period (2021-2024)

Integration and Specialization: Themes like "environmental impact," "decision making," and "ecosystems" become prominent, indicating a heightened focus on environmental sustainability, strategic decision-making processes, and ecosystem management in agriculture.

Interdisciplinary Approaches: Topics like "tourism," "economic effects," and "circular economy" reflect a broader interdisciplinary approach, showcasing connections between agriculture and fields like tourism and economic theory.

Overall, the thematic evolution shows a progression from foundational agricultural development and technology adoption to a more diversified and integrated approach encompassing sustainability, innovation, and broader economic and environmental considerations. This evolution underscores the dynamic nature of agricultural research and practice, responding to emerging challenges and opportunities in the global agricultural landscape.

Discussion

The analysis of agribusiness research publications from 2014 to 2023 reveals significant trends and patterns in the field. In the initial period (2014-2015), the number of publications was relatively low, with 29 articles in 2014 and a slight decline to 24 in 2015. This period might reflect an emerging interest or limited focus on agribusiness research. From 2021 onwards, the field experienced consistent high activity, peaking at 99 articles in 2021, followed by slight decreases to 87 articles in 2022 and 90 articles in 2023. This surge in publications indicates a growing recognition of the importance of agribusiness, particularly in light of global sustainability and technological advancements.

The distribution of agribusiness research articles across various journals highlights the field's multidisciplinary nature. Leading the list is the *Journal of Cleaner Production* with 68 articles, emphasizing the strong focus on sustainability and clean production methods within the agribusiness sector. Similar result was observed in Monteiro et al. (2023) study. However, Bannor et al. (2024) found that the *Journal of Agribusiness in Developing Economies (JADEE)*, managed by Emerald Publishing, had 7 publications, representing 12.07% of the total, with a cumulative citation count of 36. This suggests that agribusiness research also engages with the unique challenges faced by developing economies, particularly in sectors like agriculture and entrepreneurship.

Bradford's Law applied to agribusiness research sources identifies a core set of journals that contribute the majority of articles in the field. The *Journal of Cleaner Production* stands out as the most prolific source, followed by the *International Food and Agribusiness Management Review*, *Emerald Emerging Markets Case Studies*, and *Quality - Access to Success*. These journals form the core zone of agribusiness research, contributing a substantial number of articles and highlighting their pivotal role in the field.

The prominence of these journals not only shapes the volume but also the direction of agribusiness research. Journals like *The Journal of Cleaner Production* focus heavily on sustainability, encouraging research on clean production technologies, environmental impacts, and sustainable agricultural practices. This could lead to a publication bias towards environmental and sustainability-related topics, potentially at the expense of other important aspects such as technological innovation or global trade issues within agribusiness. Similarly, *International Food and Agribusiness Management Review* and *Emerald Emerging Markets Case Studies* highlight the business and management aspects of agribusiness, with an emphasis on global supply chains, food security, and market strategies. This focus might skew research toward a globalized view of agribusiness, potentially neglecting local and regional issues. On the other hand, *Quality - Access to Success* prioritizes operational efficiency, quality management, and supply chain optimization, which might limit the exploration of socio-economic factors such as small-scale farming or economic inequality. These biases in top journals could result in the marginalization of topics not aligning with sustainability or global business management, thus narrowing the scope of agribusiness research. The analysis of key contributors to agribusiness research highlights several prolific authors. Blok V stands out with 5 documents, indicating a notable impact and substantial contribution to the field. Kumar S and Morris W also make significant contributions, each authoring 4 documents. Monteiro et al. (2023) reveal that authors Kucukvar M., Ridoutt B., and Špička J. each have an h-index of 3, demonstrating that they have at least three publications with a minimum of three citations each. However, the prevalence of certain prolific authors and the emphasis on sustainability-driven research could potentially reinforce the dominant themes and narrow the diversity of topics in agribusiness.

The data exemplifies Lotka's Law, with 95% of authors having written only one document. This dominant proportion aligns with the typical productivity pattern where a small number of authors contribute the bulk of publications, while the vast majority have only one or two publications.

The affiliations of agribusiness research articles highlight the institutions most active in the field. Halmstad University, University of Novi Sad, and an unspecified category labeled "Not Reported" each top the list with 15 articles. The global distribution of agribusiness research articles shows significant contributions from the United States, India, and China, among others. Highly cited documents such as those by Dutta et al. (2020), Mangla et al. (2018), and Kumar et al. (2021) indicate significant influence and ongoing relevance in their respective fields.

The prominence of terms like "agriculture," "sustainable development," and "agricultural robots" in the word cloud reflects significant attention to sustainability, technological advancements, and environmental impacts in agribusiness research. However, the study conducted by Bannor et al. (2024) highlights a slightly different focus. Their analysis reveals that terms such as "agribusiness," "entrepreneurship," "agriculture," "Africa," "economic growth," "gender," "youth," and "developing countries" have predominantly been used across all the articles included in their study. Both perspectives provides a more holistic understanding of the current state of agribusiness research. While there is a strong emphasis on sustainability and technological innovation, there is also a significant focus on the socio-economic aspects

that are vital for fostering inclusive growth and development in agribusiness sectors globally. This highlights a unique aspect of agribusiness: its dual focus on environmental sustainability and socio-economic development.

The co-occurrence network and thematic evolution analyses reveal distinct clusters of related terms and concepts, with nodes like "agriculture," "sustainable development," and "environmental impact" playing pivotal roles. However, Monteiro et al. (2023) discover sustainable development, sustainability indicators, sustainability assessment, decision-making, agriculture, environmental protection, trade, economic analysis, sustainability performance, benchmarking and food consumption. The thematic evolution shows a progression from foundational agricultural development and technology adoption to a more diversified approach encompassing sustainability, innovation, and broader economic and environmental considerations. Thus, while agribusiness shares common ground with environmental and technological studies, it offers a distinct perspective by considering the economic and social factors that shape the field globally, particularly in developing regions.

Conclusion

The analysis reveals a progressive trajectory in agribusiness research, transitioning from initial stages of emerging interest to robust growth and recognition from 2016 onward. Key journals and prolific authors have driven the field's focus on sustainability and technology, underscoring its pivotal role in addressing global challenges. The application of bibliometric laws underscores concentrated contributions within core sources, facilitating structured dissemination. Thematic and network analyses emphasize core themes like agriculture and sustainability, reflecting the field's complexity and interdisciplinary nature. Overall, the findings emphasize the field's critical role in global sustainability efforts, necessitating ongoing collaboration and innovation to tackle diverse and evolving challenges effectively.

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